

Public Service Innovation Strategy Towards Smart Government

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze public service innovation strategies in realizing smart government and identify supporting and inhibiting factors in their implementation. Digital transformation in government is an urgent need in the information technology era, especially to improve the efficiency, transparency, and accountability of public services. This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive design. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, observations, and documentation studies of government agencies implementing digital-based public service innovations. Data analysis was conducted interactively through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. Data validity was maintained through triangulation of sources and methods. The results show that public service innovation strategies towards smart government include service digitalization, business process simplification, data integration, strengthening transformational leadership, and increasing human resource capacity. The implementation of innovations has been proven to increase service time efficiency, information transparency, and public participation.

ABSTRACT

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menganalisis strategi inovasi pelayanan publik dalam mewujudkan smart government serta mengidentifikasi faktor pendukung dan penghambat implementasinya. Transformasi digital dalam pemerintahan menjadi kebutuhan mendesak di era teknologi informasi, terutama untuk meningkatkan efisiensi, transparansi, dan akuntabilitas pelayanan publik. Penelitian ini menggunakan pendekatan kualitatif dengan desain deskriptif. Data dikumpulkan melalui wawancara mendalam, observasi, dan studi dokumentasi terhadap instansi pemerintah yang menerapkan inovasi pelayanan publik berbasis digital. Analisis data dilakukan secara interaktif melalui tahapan reduksi data, penyajian data, dan penarikan kesimpulan. Keabsahan data dijaga melalui triangulasi sumber dan metode. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa strategi inovasi pelayanan publik menuju smart government mencakup digitalisasi layanan, penyederhanaan proses bisnis, integrasi data, penguatan kepemimpinan transformasional, serta peningkatan kapasitas sumber daya manusia. Implementasi inovasi terbukti meningkatkan efisiensi waktu pelayanan, transparansi informasi, dan partisipasi masyarakat.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of information and communication technology over the past two decades has brought fundamental changes to various aspects of life, including governance. The digital revolution, marked by advances in the internet, big data, artificial intelligence, and the integration of cloud-based systems, is driving the transformation of public service models from conventional systems to faster, more transparent, and more accountable digital systems. Globally, many countries have adopted the concept of *digital government* or *smart government* as an effort to improve the quality of public services while strengthening public trust in government. This transformation goes beyond the digitization of administrative procedures, but encompasses a paradigm shift in policy management, data-driven decision-making, and public involvement in governance processes (Wijaya & Suranto, 2020).

In Indonesia, efforts towards electronic-based government have been realized through the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) policy as stipulated in Presidential Regulation Number 95 of 2018. This regulation serves as the foundation for digital transformation in the government sector, which aims to create clean, effective, transparent, and accountable

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governance. Furthermore, the government is also encouraging the acceleration of national digital transformation through various priority programs outlined in the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform (PANRB) and strengthening the integration of digital public services through the Ministry of Communication and Informatics. However, the implementation of this policy still faces various challenges, such as limited infrastructure, the digital literacy gap, resistance to change, and suboptimal inter-agency coordination (Yanuarto et al., 2025).

Public service is one of the main indicators of successful governance. Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services stipulates that public services must adhere to the principles of legal certainty, transparency, participation, professionalism, and equality. However, in practice, various problems persist, such as complicated procedures, long service times, lack of cost certainty, and low responsiveness of officials. These conditions indicate that bureaucratic reform has not yet fully resulted in excellent service. Therefore, public service innovation is an urgent need to meet the expectations of an increasingly critical and technologically savvy public (Wahyiah, 2025). The concept of *smart government* emerges as part of *smart city development*, integrating digital technology into government systems to improve efficiency, effectiveness, transparency, and public participation. Smart government focuses not only on providing application-based services but also on cross-sector data integration, system interoperability, and accurate data analysis-based decision-making. In this context, innovation strategies are key to ensuring that digital transformation does not stop at an administrative formality but rather truly creates added value for society (Wanto, 2019).

Public service innovation strategies encompass several important dimensions, including technological innovation, business process innovation, policy innovation, and organizational culture innovation. Technological innovation relates to the use of digital platforms, mobile applications, online queuing systems, and the integration of one-stop-shop services. Business process innovation demands procedural simplification through a *business process reengineering approach*, thereby streamlining service flows to become simpler and more efficient. Policy innovation demands regulations that adapt to technological developments, while organizational culture innovation emphasizes a shift in the mindset of officials from *a rule-based bureaucracy* to *a service-oriented bureaucracy*. Without a change in organizational culture, digitalization will simply shift manual procedures to electronic systems without improving service quality (Rusdin, 2025).

Furthermore, implementing smart government also requires the support of competent human resources who are adaptable to change. Digital transformation is not only about hardware and software, but also about the readiness of civil servants to manage technology-based systems. Continuous training, improving digital literacy, and strengthening transformational leadership are crucial factors in driving successful public service innovation. Visionary leadership can create an organizational climate that supports experimentation, collaboration, and continuous learning (Erlangga, 2025). Another challenge in implementing smart government is data security and protecting public privacy. Data integration between agencies has the potential to improve service efficiency, but also poses the risk of data breaches if not managed with adequate security systems. Therefore, innovation strategies must be accompanied by robust data governance policies, including cybersecurity standards, digital audit mechanisms, and personal data protection regulations (Wirawan et al., 2025).

Furthermore, the smart government approach emphasizes the importance of collaboration between government, the private sector, academia, and civil society within a *quadruple helix framework*. This collaboration enables co-creation in the provision of public services, where the public is not only the object of service but also the subject, actively participating in formulating solutions. Digital-based public participation, such as *e-participation* and *e-consultation*, can strengthen transparency and enhance the legitimacy of government policies (Vienessa et al., 2025). In the regional context, smart government implementation often faces disparities in fiscal capacity and infrastructure between regions. Urban areas are relatively more prepared to adopt technology than remote areas, which still face limitations in internet access and technological devices. Therefore, innovation strategies must consider local conditions

and adopt a phased and sustainable approach to avoid gaps in public services (Hardiyansyah, 2024).

Based on this description, it is clear that the transformation toward smart government is not an instant process, but rather requires a comprehensive, integrated, and sustainable innovation strategy. This strategy must encompass aspects of regulation, technology, human resources, data governance, and public participation. Without a well-thought-out strategy, public service innovation risks becoming a short-term project that does not significantly impact service quality (Aushap et al., 2023).

Thus, research on public service innovation strategies toward smart government is highly relevant for identifying key success factors, analyzing implementation challenges, and formulating applicable policy recommendations. This research is expected to provide theoretical contributions to the development of public administration and digital governance studies, while also providing practical assistance to the government in designing responsive, adaptive, and community-oriented public service innovation policies in the digital era.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach with the aim of gaining a deeper understanding of public service innovation strategies for realizing smart government. A qualitative approach was chosen because it can explore the meanings, perceptions, experiences, and dynamics that occur during the implementation of digital-based public service innovations. The research focuses not only on the final results but also on the processes, interactions between actors, and the policy context and organizational culture that influence the success of digital transformation in government.

The data sources in this study consist of primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained through in-depth interviews with key informants such as agency leaders, Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) administrators, service implementers, and the public as service users. Informants were selected purposively based on their involvement in and understanding of public service innovation. Furthermore, data were collected through direct observation of digital-based service processes and documentation studies of relevant regulations, performance reports, and policy documents.

Data analysis was conducted interactively through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. Data obtained from interviews, observations, and documentation were selected, categorized, and then interpreted to identify patterns and themes related to public service innovation strategies toward smart government. Data validity was maintained through triangulation of sources and methods, as well as reconfirmation with informants (member checks). With this method, the research is expected to produce a comprehensive and contextual understanding of the government's efforts to develop digital-based public services.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of field research, the implementation of public service innovation strategies towards smart government shows significant changes in service governance, particularly in the aspects of service digitalization, system integration, and increased transparency. The agencies studied have developed various electronic-based service platforms that enable the public to access services online, ranging from administrative applications and permits to public complaints. This transformation has resulted in time and cost efficiency, both for the public and for the government organization itself. Service processes that previously required several manual and face-to-face stages can now be carried out through an integrated system, thereby reducing queues, accelerating service completion times, and minimizing the potential for maladministration (Suprpto et al., 2026).

In addition to service digitization, research results show that innovation strategies also include business process simplification. Before implementing digital systems, many service procedures were layered and bureaucratic. Through innovation, agencies evaluated Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and eliminated inefficient steps. This simplification is crucial

because digitalization without process reform will only shift manual complexity into electronic systems. Therefore, bureaucratic reform goes hand in hand with digital transformation to ensure that innovation truly improves service quality. In terms of data integration, the study found efforts to develop interoperability between units and agencies (Mozin, Pakaya, et al., 2025). Data integration enables the rapid and accurate exchange of information, thereby reducing the duplication of documents that were previously frequently requested by the public. With a centralized database, decision-making becomes more evidence-based (evidence-based policy), as leaders can access performance reports and service data in real time. This demonstrates that smart government focuses not only on front office services but also on strengthening the government's internal management system (Siregar, 2023).

However, the success of an innovation strategy is heavily influenced by leadership. Interviews indicate that leadership commitment is a key factor in driving organizational change. Visionary and transformational leadership can create a work culture that adapts to technology and encourages cross-sector collaboration. Leaders act as change agents, providing policy support, budget allocation, and motivation to staff to innovate. Without such support, innovation tends to stagnate and become merely administrative (Sangaji & Irianto, 2025). Besides leadership, human resource (HR) capacity is another crucial factor. Research shows that there is still a digital competency gap among civil servants, especially among those unfamiliar with technology-based systems. To address this, agencies conduct regular training and technical assistance. However, the adaptation process is not always smooth due to resistance to change. Some civil servants feel that digital systems increase their workload or reduce their discretion in carrying out their duties. This situation demonstrates that public service innovation is not only a technological issue but also involves changes in organizational culture (Sultana et al., 2023).

From the perspective of the public as service users, digital innovation has a positive impact on ease of access, transparency of information, and certainty of service times and costs. The public can monitor the status of service requests online without having to visit the office in person. Furthermore, online complaint channels allow the public to submit complaints more quickly and with proper documentation. This increases government accountability in responding to public needs (Iswanto & Kunci, 2025). However, research also finds that not all groups can optimally utilize digital services, particularly the elderly or those with limited internet access. The digital divide presents a real challenge to the implementation of smart government (Hidayatullah & Pratama, 2025). From a data governance perspective, research findings indicate that information security and personal data protection are key areas of innovation strategy. System integration and the use of centralized databases increase efficiency, but also pose the risk of data breaches if not accompanied by adequate cybersecurity systems. Therefore, agencies have begun implementing digital security standards, authorization-based access restrictions, and regular system audits. These steps are crucial for maintaining public trust in government digital services (Mozin, Abdullah, et al., 2025).

Further discussion shows that successful smart government implementation requires a collaborative approach. The study found collaboration between the government and the private sector in application development and technological infrastructure support. Furthermore, collaboration with academics and digital communities also contributes to the development of innovations based on community needs. This collaborative approach reinforces the concept of co-creation in public services, where the public is not merely the object of services but also plays a role as a partner in system improvement (Anjas et al., 2024). Overall, the research results show that the public service innovation strategy towards smart government has had a positive impact in improving efficiency, transparency, and service quality. However, its implementation still faces various challenges, such as limited infrastructure, the digital literacy gap, organizational cultural resistance, and data security issues. Therefore, the innovation strategy needs to be implemented comprehensively and sustainably, taking into account regulatory aspects, strengthening human resources, data governance, and expanding technology access for all levels of society. The transformation towards smart government is not an end in itself, but rather an ongoing process that requires commitment, adaptation, and continuous evaluation to meet the dynamics of public needs in the digital era (Pangestu & Anggraini, 2019).

CONCLUSION

Based on research findings, public service innovation strategies toward smart government have been proven to improve efficiency, transparency, and accountability. Service digitization, business process simplification, and data integration between units are key factors in accelerating service times and minimizing maladministration. This transformation not only improves the quality of public services but also strengthens the government's internal management system through data-driven decision-making.

However, the success of smart government implementation is determined not only by the availability of technology, but also by leadership commitment, human resource readiness, and changes in organizational culture. Challenges such as apparatus resistance, the digital literacy gap among the public, limited infrastructure, and data security issues remain obstacles that need to be systematically addressed. Therefore, smart government is a continuous transformation process that requires a comprehensive, collaborative, and adaptive innovation strategy that adapts to the dynamics of technological developments and public needs.

SUGGESTION

1. Strengthening Human Resources Capacity

The government needs to improve the digital competence of civil servants through ongoing training, certification, and technical assistance to enable them to optimally manage technology-based systems.

2. Digital Infrastructure Development

Equal distribution of information technology infrastructure is needed, especially in areas that still have limited internet access, to reduce the digital divide in public services.

3. Strengthening Data Governance and Security

The government needs to strengthen cybersecurity systems, personal data protection standards, and digital audit mechanisms to maintain public trust in electronic-based services.

4. Increasing Public Participation

The development of digital participation channels such as online complaints, public satisfaction surveys, and public consultation forums needs to be optimized so that the public can be actively involved in evaluating and improving services.

5. Continuous Evaluation and Innovation

Smart government implementation must be accompanied by regular evaluations of system effectiveness and its impact on service quality. The government needs to foster a culture of continuous innovation so that digital transformation doesn't stop at the administrative formality stage.

By implementing these suggestions, it is hoped that the public service innovation strategy can run more effectively and make a real contribution to realizing modern, responsive, and community-oriented governance.

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